

A Novel Method of Synthesis of Lanthanum Alkoxide

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The synthesis of alkoxides of praseodymium, neodymium and samarium has been carried out by a new method using anhydrous lanthanum trichloroacetates instead of anhydrous chlorides. The absorption spectra, IR and TGA of praseodymium isopropoxide have been investigated.

ALKOXIDES of Lanthanide Elements have been prepared by Misra et al¹ using anhydrous lanthanide chlorides and sodium isopropoxide in dry benzene. In this method anhydrous lanthanide chlorides were refluxed in dry isopropanol and on cooling the alcoholate crystallized out from the clear solution. To this crystallized mass was added a calculated (3 moles) amount of sodium isopropoxide in benzene. The lanthanum isopropoxide, being soluble, was obtained by evaporating excess solvent.

But in new method, the tris trichloroacetates of lanthanide elements were prepared from metal carbonates and trichloroacetic acid. The tris hydrated trichloroacetates were made anhydrous by keeping them in vacuum desiccator for 3 days over anhydrous CaCl_2 or by heating them under reduced pressure at 60° for 10 hrs. The anhydrous trichloroacetate, thus obtained was dissolved in anhydrous isopropanol and to this solution was added a calculated (3 moles) amount of sodium isopropoxide in large excess of benzene. The solution was refluxed for 1 hr., cooled and filtered and a clear solution was obtained. A crystalline product was obtained by evaporating the solvent to dryness under reduced pressure.

Absorption spectrum ($400\text{-}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$), infrared spectrum ($4000\text{-}250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and thermogravimetric analysis of praseodymium isopropoxide is also reported. The values of oscillator strength² (P), nephelauxetic effect³ (β) and bonding parameter⁴ ($b^{\frac{1}{2}}$) have also been computed using standard methods.

Experimental

All glass apparatus with standard interchangeable joints was used throughout this investigation.

Praseodymium, neodymium and samarium were estimated as their oxides by first precipitating them as oxalates. Alkoxy contents were determined by the chromate oxidimetry⁵.

Preparation of anhydrous trichloroacetates :

Anhydrous praseodymium, neodymium and samarium trichloroacetates were prepared from their tris hydrated trichloroacetates (which were prepared from lanthanum carbonates and trichloroacetic acid) by heating them under reduced pressure at 60° for 10 hrs.

Preparation of isopropoxides :

Anhydrous praseodymium trichloroacetate (6.43 gm) was dissolved in dry isopropanol (50 g) by refluxing. A solution of sodium isopropoxide (prepared by dissolving sodium (0.62 g) in a mixture of isopropanol and benzene (100 g) was added dropwise to this trichloroacetate solution, whereupon a white solid separated out. The solution was refluxed for 1 hr., cooled and filtered and a clear green solution was obtained. A crystalline green product was obtained by evaporating the solvent to dryness under reduced pressure at room temperature (yield 3.1 g) (Found : Pr, 44.41 ; OC_3H_7^i , 55.22 ; Calc for $\text{Pr}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7^i)_3$: Pr, 44.21 ; OC_3H_7^i , 55.79%).

Neodymium and samarium isopropoxide were prepared similarly by adding sodium isopropoxide in benzene to a solution of their trichloroacetates in isopropanol.

(Found : Nd, 44.50 ; OC_3H_7^i , 55.12 ; Calc. for $\text{Nd}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7^i)_3$: Nd, 44.90 ; OC_3H_7^i , 55.10%).

(Found : Sm, 45.18 ; OC_3H_7^i , 54.82 ; Calc. for $\text{Sm}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7^i)_3$: Sm, 45.94 ; OC_3H_7^i , 54.06%).

Absorption spectrum of $\text{Pr}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ was recorded using a Spekol (Carl Zeiss) Spectrophotometer using benzene as solvent (concentration 0.1 M). Extreme precautions were taken to avoid its hydrolysis. The cells used were provided with standard interchangeable joints.

Infrared spectra of Nujol Mull of the sample was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 Spectrophotometer.

Thermogravimetric analysis of $\text{Pr}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ was carried out on a STANTON Thermobalance Model AD-2. Thermogram was obtained on 346 mg sample and at 4°min^{-1} heating rate.

Results and Discussion

This method of obtaining alkoxide has several advantage over the conventional synthetic technique¹.

1. The dehydration of trichloroacetate is quite simple by merely keeping it in a vacuum desiccator for 3 days or by heating under reduced pressure at 60° for 10 hrs.
2. The yield is almost quantitative.
3. Sodium trichloroacetate can quantitatively be converted into trichloroacetic acid.

Thermogravimetric analysis reveal a break at 220° . The loss in weight corresponds to olefinic hydrocarbon $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$. After $\sim 290^\circ$ again we find another sharp break which continues upto $\sim 325^\circ$. During this range molecule appears to lose another molecule of olefin. In order to confirm above, alkoxide was taken in a quickfit flask provided with a take off and was slowly heated to 220° . There was change in the monometer. The collected gas was allowed to come into contact with a very dilute and cold solution of KMnO_4 which it decolourized indicating thereby that gas is olefin. The same observation was repeated at $\sim 325^\circ$ which again supported our assumption that another molecule of olefin was given off. The residue left after 570° was found to be Pr_6O_{11} .

isobramching, while 1130 cm^{-1} band is thought to be an alkyl absorption induced by proximity of oxygen atom. The intensity of 1120 cm^{-1} band suggests that it is essentially an oxygen to carbon stretching absorption⁶. The stretching vibrations at 1378, 1310 and 1260 cm^{-1} are actually split bands characteristic of two terminal methyl group on the same carbon atom. A strong band at 1020 cm^{-1} is due to predominantly C-O stretching modes of Pr-O-C group and not Pr-O as suggested by earlier workers⁷. The Pr-O stretching region of the praseodymium isopropoxide spectrum provides evidences for intermolecular bonding through oxygen. Several Pr-O bands observed in this region appear most probably due to the presence of bridging oxygen.

Absorption spectrum of praseodymium isopropoxide in benzene is reported for the first time. Different transitions have been assigned. The low intensity of the bands (oscillator strength $P \sim 10^{-6}$) suggests that all the bands are due to forbidden electric dipole transitions. These transitions occur between ground state, and excited state of f^n configurations. The positive value of nephelauxetic ratio (0.9976) indicating thereby that the nature of bonding between metal and ligand is covalent as compared to lanthanon aquo ion. The smaller value of bonding parameter $b^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (0.0489) suggests that 4f orbitals are very slightly involved in bonding in lanthanon alkoxide. Reactions of praseodymium, neodymium and samarium isopropoxide with o-phenanthroline, α, α' dipyridyl and thiourea have also been investigated and the result will be communicated later on.

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TABLE 1—ENERGY AND INTENSITY (IN TERMS OF OSCILLATOR STRENGTH P) OF THE BANDS OF PRASEODYMIUM ISOPROPOXIDE.

Spectral region cm^{-1}	Levels	ν (cm^{-1})	$P \times 10^6$ (Expt.)
16000-17500	1D_2	17065	2.1
20200-21000	3P_0	20833	2.2
21000-22100	3P_1	21408	3.1
22100-23500	3P_2	22471	11.6

Infrared spectra :

The characteristic absorption occur at or very close to 1170 cm^{-1} , has been identified as characteristics of

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